

Research Paper

Revisiting strain localization from the view of structured inhomogeneity

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ABSTRACT

Strain localization in sandy geomaterials, particularly shear band formation, is influenced by loading conditions, boundary constraints, constitutive behavior, and initial inhomogeneity. Among these factors, the effect of inhomogeneity has often been inadequately represented in numerical studies, either through unstructured randomness or insufficient quantitative analysis across multiple realizations. This study revisits the problem by combining a systematic review of existing literature with extended simulations that emphasize the role of structured state fields. A conditional random field method is employed to generate spatially correlated void ratio distributions that reflect material heterogeneity. Simulations conducted under idealized boundary conditions and using a simple, void ratio-dependent constitutive model show that structured inhomogeneity alone can initiate and guide shear band development in ways consistent with experimental observations. Analysis from a dilatancy perspective reveals how spatial variation in void ratio governs the localization of volumetric strain and influences shear band's evolution. To further interpret micromechanical mechanisms, two simplified modeling frameworks are introduced: one based on void ratio-dependent elasticity and another representing a two-element structural idealization. These approaches help clarify how micro-scale heterogeneity gives rise to macroscopic deformation patterns, even without advanced constitutive formulations. This study emphasizes that an accurate representation of initial state inhomogeneity is crucial for understanding strain localization and the resulting macroscopic behavior. Accordingly, this factor should be explicitly accounted for in both experimental interpretation and the development and calibration of constitutive models.

1. Introduction

The inhomogeneity of geomaterials is widely recognized as one of their fundamental characteristics. This inhomogeneity manifests in the spatial variability of their structure, physical properties, and mechanical behavior. Examples include the non-uniform distribution of particle shapes and mineral compositions (Towhata, 1996; Kawamoto et al., 2018), the randomness in void ratio or fabric, the orientation of bedding or jointing, and the spatial variation of mechanical parameters such as strength, stiffness, permeability, and shear wave velocity (Rovithis et al., 2011; Rovithis and Mylonakis, 2022). In numerical modeling of sandy soil behavior using the finite element method, such inhomogeneity can be reflected not only in the mechanical parameters but also in the spatial distribution of state variables. At the field scale, spatial variability is often represented by modeling key constitutive parameters such as undrained shear strength, cohesion, friction angle, and permeability as random fields (Jiang et al., 2022). At the scale of laboratory specimens, the material is typically assumed to be uniform in composition, as the

samples are carefully prepared from a single material under controlled conditions. This assumption allows the use of a single constitutive model with a unified set of material-specific parameters. To calibrate these parameters, laboratory data are typically associated with a specific initial state (e.g., initial void ratio and confining pressure), which serves as the basis for following parameter estimation.

It is well known that the mechanical response of sandy soils is strongly dependent on both the effective pressure level and the void ratio. These two factors significantly influence the material's response to loading. Beyond these, some advanced constitutive models incorporate fabric components to account for the material's internal structural anisotropy (Dafalias et al., 2004). Although the initial pressure within a specimen can be assumed uniform, experimental evidence suggests that the initial distributions of void ratio and fabric are not homogeneous (Kido and Higo, 2017; Wiebicke et al., 2017). Consequently, even though laboratory records are commonly regarded as single-element tests performed on homogeneous media, in essence, they are observations of the behavior of granular assemblies. This perspective helps

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explain the occurrence of various forms of strain localization under different loading conditions (Le et al., 2022), such as the development of a distinct shear plane dividing the specimen into two parts (Colliat-Dangus, 1986). In fact, strain localization in the form of shear bands is observed in most laboratory tests (Desrues and Chambon, 2002; Ali-karami et al., 2015; Desrues et al., 2018), even in small specimens with dimensions as small as 11 mm in diameter and 22 mm in height (Kawamoto et al., 2018).

For advanced nonlinear constitutive models, the influence of the initial state becomes more pronounced. Spatial inhomogeneity in the initial state can lead to specific and complex model responses. For instance, non-uniform distributions of void ratio may trigger strain localization (Nübel and Karcher, 1998). These phenomena reflect the collective behavior of granular assemblies at the macroscale, rather than the intrinsic response of a representative element (Le et al., 2022). This discrepancy presents challenges in both the calibration and validation of constitutive models (Romero-Olán et al., 2024). If laboratory tests are interpreted strictly as representations of idealized element responses, many observed complexities remain unexplained, often prompting the development of highly sophisticated constitutive frameworks. Alternatively, treating the test as a boundary value problem requires detailed modeling of the specimen's internal structure and spatially variable state parameters, in order to understand how microstructural features affect macroscopic behavior.

Strain localization generally appears as shear bands or bifurcation in experiments. Numerous experimental studies have explored the influence of state parameters on strain localization. For example, Bauer (1999) examined strain localization behavior under biaxial compression and found that lower void ratio and higher stress ratios tend to induce bifurcation at lower axial strains. Wu et al. (2020) observed that lower confining pressure and higher initial void ratio can delay the onset of shear band formation. The symmetry constraints in conventional triaxial tests may also suppress localization, resulting in stiffer global responses (Romero-Olán et al., 2024). Wanatowski and Chu (2006) reported that when the state parameter is positive (i.e. $e > e_c$), no observable shear band develops regardless of whether drainage is allowed. Strain localization has been widely observed in triaxial tests (Takano et al., 2015).

In numerical modeling, various approaches have been adopted to investigate the formation of strain localization. Tejchman and Wu (1996) checked the ability of hypoplasticity to model strain localization. Teunissen (2008) demonstrated that even an elastic-perfectly plastic Mohr–Coulomb model can reproduce strain localization when applied in finite element simulations of biaxial tests. Using discrete element modeling with elliptical particles, Mahmood and Iwashita (2011) observed the emergence of large voids and intense particle rotation concentrated within X-shaped shear bands. Griffiths et al. (2012) employed Monte Carlo simulations to examine the relationship between effective Young's modulus and the random distribution of void ratio and pore size in idealized blocks. Their findings showed that void ratio has a significant impact on effective stiffness. Additionally, the presence of fine inclusions was found to influence the packing structure and mechanical response of granular mixtures (Chang et al., 2015; Othman and Marto, 2018). When the content of fines is low, the statistical reliability of void ratio-related indices, such as the relationship between maximum and minimum void ratios, improves (Cubrinovski and Ishihara, 2002). For this reason, this study focuses exclusively on clean sands, excluding mixtures containing fine particles.

Collectively, previous studies indicate that the onset and development of strain localization are affected by a range of factors, including boundary conditions, stress level, void ratio, end constraints, loading mode, and strain rate (Lee, 1970; Alshibli et al., 2003; Suzuki and Yamada, 2006). Among these, the influence of initial inhomogeneity has not received enough attention, primarily due to limitations in available experimental techniques. However, the present work shows that the initial state has a direct and complex effect on the observed macroscopic behavior. Even under idealized boundary conditions and loading

control, the response remains sensitive to both the material-specific constitutive behavior and the internal structure of the specimen. This highlights two complementary perspectives. On one hand, complex macroscopic phenomena may be captured using advanced constitutive models under the assumption of homogeneity (Zhang et al., 2021; Fan et al., 2024). On the other hand, by treating laboratory tests as boundary value problems and explicitly modeling the spatial distribution of initial state variables, even relatively simple constitutive models can reproduce intricate macroscopic responses.

This study aims to build upon previous research by explicitly accounting for the influence of inhomogeneous state parameters on strain localization in a more realistic and systematic manner. In particular, it seeks to identify and interpret the most relevant underlying mechanisms contributing to localization phenomena. To achieve this, the study employs the conditional random field (CRF) approach to investigate the role of structured inhomogeneity in the evolution of strain localization.

The simulation results demonstrate that variability in void ratio, as one of the most fundamental state variables, can alone give rise to a series of characteristic macroscopic behaviors. These include the initiation of shear bands, the geometric evolution of localization zones, and mechanical contrasts between localized and non-localized regions. Notably, these effects can be reproduced without relying on advanced constitutive formulations. Through multiple simulations and quantitative analyses, the study reveals a clear link between fluctuations in state variables at the micro scale and strain localization at the macro scale. Based on these findings, a simplified structural model and a state-variable gradient mechanism are proposed to interpret the observed coupling between the initial inhomogeneity and the resulting macroscopic behavior.

2. Methodology

2.1. Structured Void ratio Field

Void ratio is an integrated reflection of a soil's mechanical characteristics (Shen et al., 2019). The range of void ratio values can directly indicate certain mechanical properties, such as stiffness and strength, as shown by Cubrinovski and Ishihara (1999). Typical void ratio ranges for representative sands can be found in the work of Zheng and Hryciw (2016). The spatial distribution of void ratio within a specimen is inherently inhomogeneous. However, this inhomogeneity cannot be adequately captured using purely random variables or conventional random fields. A meaningful representation requires a macroscopic model of void ratio distribution that accounts for spatial correlation and structural dependencies (Wu et al., 2004).

Shahinpoor (1981, 1983) employed optical scanning and recording techniques to study the void ratio distribution in single-layer packings of spherical cohesionless particles. The results revealed that void ratio follows a biased Maxwellian trend with the Maxwellian tail favored towards the population of denser "Voronoi Cells." Furthermore, these statistical characterizations can be generalized to three dimensional fabrics through standard stereological theorems. The probability density function (PDF) is given by

$$f(e) = \frac{\lambda \exp(-\lambda e)}{\exp(-\lambda e_m) - \exp(-\lambda e_M)} \quad (1)$$

where e_m and e_M are the minimum and maximum void ratio, respectively. The parameter λ can be obtained by solving the following transcendental equation

$$\bar{e} = \lambda^{-1} + \frac{e_m \exp(-\lambda e_m) - e_M \exp(-\lambda e_M)}{\exp(-\lambda e_m) - \exp(-\lambda e_M)} \quad (2)$$

where \bar{e} is the average void ratio, which can be measured globally. Bhatia and Soliman (1990), using a computer-controlled image analyzer, observed that the spatial density of denser voids tends to

decrease as particle shape changes from spherical to angular. They further proposed that the frequency distribution of void ratio for both Ottawa sand and crystalline silica sand can be modelled using the beta distribution:

$$f(e) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + \beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)}(e_M - e_m)^{\beta-1}(e - e_m)^{\alpha-1}(e_M - e)^{\beta-1} \quad (3)$$

In this equation, Γ denotes the gamma function, while α and β are shape parameters that vary with the relative density and are determined through fitting. The gamma function in this context cannot be evaluated analytically and must be computed using numerical integration or approximated through series expansion. Although this density function differs in form from Equation (1), both describe a similar trend. For a given macroscopic void ratio, the probability distribution is inherently nonlinear:

$$f_E(e) \propto \exp(-\lambda e), e \in [e_m, e_M] \quad (4)$$

which is a truncated exponential distribution. Several studies have proposed experimental and image-based techniques to analyse the distribution of local void ratio in cohesionless particle assemblies or soils (Ghalib and Hryciw, 1999; Sammartino et al., 2002; Al-Raoush and Alshibli, 2006; Wang et al., 2024). However, these studies either did not provide a reference distribution function, or they were limited to relatively narrow void ratio ranges, or their results were significantly influenced by the choice of box size (Song et al., 2015). In comparison, Eq. (1) involves fewer parameters and offers greater practical applicability. This study therefore adopts that formulation to describe the distribution of void ratio. The model requires only macroscopic void ratio, along with the maximum and minimum void ratio values, which can be readily obtained from standard laboratory tests. Its simplicity makes it convenient and efficient for use in numerical simulations.

Some studies have also employed unstructured random density fields, in which the void ratio values at different spatial locations are assumed to be mutually independent (Andrade and Borja, 2006). According to Jiang et al. (2022), such unstructured random fields often overestimate the variance of spatial parameters, since they do not incorporate prior information to constrain the spatial distribution. This lack of spatial correlation can in turn affect the failure modes observed in numerical models.

While a substantial body of literature addresses the scale of fluctuation (SoF) for field-scale soil properties, there is limited research on SoF at the specimen scale. Rodriguez-Dono et al. (2023) suggested that the correlation length at the laboratory scale can be estimated by fitting to observed data. A smaller scale of fluctuation allows for steeper gradients in void ratio and therefore provides a better fit to a given prior probability density function. In this study, the selection of SoF is guided by two principles: it must respect the physical constraints imposed by the finite element size, and it should enable a close match to the assumed prior distribution of void ratio.

It is generally recognized that the horizontal scale of fluctuation tends to be at least one order of magnitude greater than the vertical scale (Phoon and Kulhawy, 1999). However, such statistical characterization is also lacking in laboratory specimens. For the given experimental material, well-defined covariance functions and corresponding correlation lengths may be identified through sensitivity analysis or parameter optimization, based on sufficient experimental analysis and statistics of microscopic void ratio. However, due to the lack of sufficient experimental data, this inverse process cannot yet be completed. In the present study, both the exponential and Gaussian autocorrelation functions are examined. These functions allow the generation of a structured conditional random field for the initial void ratio.

The unconditional random field $Z(x)$ was generated using the GSTools library (Müller et al., 2022). This field was then transformed to obtain a structured conditional random field according to the following expression:

$$E(x) = F^{-1}(\Phi(Z(x))) \quad (5)$$

where Φ denotes the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the standard normal distribution, and F^{-1} is the inverse CDF corresponding to $f(e)$. This transformation method enables the robust generation of conditional random fields under various choices of covariance functions and correlation lengths. Fig. 1 presents a comparison between random realizations and the theoretical model for loose, medium, and dense samples. Samples 1, 2, and 3 represent different realizations of the void ratio field under the same target macroscopic void ratio, illustrating the variability in internal structure that can occur during sample generation. The results show a close agreement between the generated conditional random fields and the target probability distributions.

To further compare the proposed method with conventional approaches, Fig. 2(a, b) presents the spatial distribution and histogram of a structured void ratio field generated at a relative density of 20 %. In contrast, Fig. 2(c, d) shows the void ratio distribution and histogram generated by assigning only the target mean void ratio and an approximate void range, without enforcing spatial structure. Evidently, the latter exhibits not only greater randomness, but more importantly, lacks the ability to capture the influence of factors such as specimen preparation, gravity, and other mechanisms that may affect fabric development. Moreover, simulations based on such unstructured void ratio fields are more prone to convergence issues.

Advanced constitutive models that include fabric tensors introduce additional state variables. These models can offer more precise control over structural inhomogeneity in numerical simulations, and thus may provide deeper insight into the mechanisms underlying strain localization. However, a significant limitation is that fabric information is not directly measurable in experiments, and there is currently a lack of theoretical guidance on its macroscopic distribution. Further research is needed before these models can be systematically applied in this context.

2.2. Modeling Procedure

Plane strain conditions are representative of many geotechnical scenarios, such as road embankments and tailing dams (He et al., 2025). Furthermore, laboratory tests under plane strain have been shown to be a preferred configuration for observing strain localization phenomena (Wanatowski and Chu, 2007). This study focuses on simulating drained plane strain conditions, following the modeling procedure outlined below:

- Construction of the geometric model and mesh generation
- Extraction of centroid coordinates for each element
- Generation of the initial void ratio field using a conditional random field based on the centroid locations
- Application of initial confining stress and boundary constraints, followed by axial displacement loading
- Post-processing and analysis of the output data

To demonstrate that complex material behavior can be captured without requiring sophisticated constitutive formulations, this study adopts the original version of the hypoplastic model proposed by von Wolffersdorff (1996). This model is capable of reflecting both pressure-dependent and void ratio-dependent behavior in a nonlinear framework. As long as the basic composition of the material remains unchanged, for example, without particle crushing, the hypoplastic model can reproduce a wide range of stress-strain behaviors using a single, consistent parameter set (Herle and Gudehus, 1999).

In this context, the hypoplastic model is considered material-specific. The same constitutive formulation and parameter set are applied throughout the specimen. Consequently, macroscopic behavior is governed only by the initial spatial distribution of state variables. All

Fig. 1. Compare empirical PDF with theoretical PDF: (a) loose; (b) medium dense; (c) dense.

Fig. 2. Random void ratio field by: (a,b) conditional structured method; (c,d) weakly conditional unstructured method;

material parameters and relevant properties follow the values and guidelines reported by [Wichtmann and Triantafyllidis \(2016\)](#).

2.3. Details of Modeling

2.3.1. Geometry and mesh

Various specimen dimensions have been adopted in biaxial experiments and numerical simulations. Examples include $60 \times 60 \times 120$ mm ([Wanatowski and Chu, 2012](#)), $40 \times 80 \times 140$ mm ([Han and Drescher, 1993](#); [Mooney et al., 1998](#)), $80.8 \times 83.3 \times 152.4$ mm ([Alshibli et al., 2003](#)), and a width-to-height ratio of 1:4 ([Teunissen, 2008](#)). Similar variations are also found in laboratory testing of shear bands using Conventional Triaxial Compression (CTC) devices. Commonly used specimen sizes include cubic samples of $75 \times 75 \times 150$ mm, cylindrical samples of 39.1 mm in diameter and 80 mm in height ([Ma et al., 2024](#)), and samples of 40 mm in diameter and 80 mm in height ([Liu et al., 2024](#)). In this study, a plane strain specimen with a width of 40 mm and a height of 80 mm is modelled in Abaqus. Four-node plane strain elements (CPE4) are used for meshing.

The mesh design must meet two key requirements. The first is the accuracy of numerical calculations. The second is compatibility with the generation of conditional random fields. According to [Borja et al. \(2013\)](#), beyond approximately 3 % nominal vertical strain, the model response becomes dependent on the mesh size. Further, [Lin et al. \(2015\)](#) showed that if the mesh size is well chosen, numerical predictions remain consistent with laboratory results even at large axial strains. More advanced meshing techniques have also been proposed to capture extensive strain localization ([Monforte et al., 2019](#)). Therefore, meshing strategy plays a critical role in model reliability.

For unconditional random fields, the mesh element size should not

exceed half the scale of fluctuation ([Huang and Griffiths, 2015](#)). When an exponential autocorrelation function is used, [Jiang and Huang \(2018\)](#) suggested that the element size must be smaller than 0.25 times the fluctuation scale. To ensure computational accuracy while allowing a detailed representation of spatial variability, the model uses square elements of 1.25 mm by 1.25 mm. A total of 2048 elements are generated. For quantifying the width of shear bands, an additional mesh configuration is employed using square elements of 0.5 mm by 0.5 mm. All other modeling conditions remain unchanged.

2.3.2. Initial and boundary conditions

A constant lateral confining pressure is applied along the sides of the specimen. The center of the bottom boundary is fixed, and vertical displacements are restricted for all nodes along the bottom edge. This setup assumes no friction between the specimen and the loading platens. The omission of interface friction is intended to avoid end constraints, which may otherwise induce non-uniform deformation patterns and artificial strain softening due to frictional effects ([Chu and Wanatowski, 2009](#)).

This boundary configuration is illustrated in [Fig. 3\(a\)](#), where the contour indicates void ratio. [Fig. 3\(b\)](#) shows the initial void ratio distribution and the distribution after axial loading of one realization. The patterns are consistent with experimental observations and findings from discrete element simulations ([Kido and Higo, 2017](#)). This comparison supports the validity of the conditional random field generation method and confirms the appropriateness of the modeling setup.

In addition to the structured random void ratio field described above, further simulations were carried out using specimens with void ratio variation only in the horizontal or vertical direction. Details of these cases are presented in [Section 3.3](#).

Fig. 3. One realization of simulation: (a) model configuration; (b) void ratio distribution along specimen height; (c) unstructured void ratio.

3. Global Behavior

In this study, random fields were generated using different combinations of covariance functions and correlation distances. For each random field realization, simulations were conducted under varying initial relative densities and confining pressures. The specimens evolved towards one of two states. In the first case, the model successfully converged to a target axial strain of 25 %. In the second case, convergence failed, and the simulation was terminated at an intermediate loading stage. Both outcomes are collectively referred to as the final state.

3.1. Characteristic Patterns and General Observations

Based on the deformation patterns observed at the final state, the simulation results can be categorized into three types: no shear band (including cases that failed to converge at the target axial strain), single shear band, and multiple shear bands. Out of more than 100 simulations,

the final-state outcomes can be summarized as follows: 45 cases either did not converge or showed no identifiable shear band (diffuse mode, Darve et al., 2021), 15 cases showed a single shear band, and 46 cases exhibited multiple shear bands. This ratio should not be interpreted as a strict quantitative indicator, as many of the cases without a clearly formed shear band terminated early due to convergence issues at low levels of axial deformation. It is anticipated that the occurrence of shear bands would be more frequent if alternative state-dependent constitutive models were employed or if the convergence criteria were relaxed. Representative examples of the final shear strain states are illustrated in Fig. 4.

In the present study, clear shear bands were observed across all specimen types, regardless of their initial relative density (ranging from loose to dense) or the applied confining pressure (from 0.1 MPa to 2 MPa). Although some earlier studies have suggested that shear band formation is unlikely in loose samples, findings have not been consistent. For instance, in the experiments by Wanatowski and Chu (2006a), no observable shear bands were reported when the state parameter was

Fig. 4. Typical deformation modes (shear strain ϵ_{12}) at the final state: (a, b) no shear band; (c, d) single shear band; (e, f) multiple shear bands.

positive (i.e., $e > e_c$), regardless of drainage conditions. In contrast, several other studies reported the presence of shear bands in plane strain tests involving loose sand, such as Finno et al. (1997). Some researchers even suggested that shear bands inevitably develop under non-uniform confining pressures (Chu et al., 1996; Chu and Wanatowski, 2009). Distinct strain localization has also been reported in undrained plane strain conditions (Finno et al., 1996), although some attribute this to experimental artefacts or procedural details (Suzuki and Yamada, 2006).

The development of shear bands is a gradual process (Xiong et al., 2025), which may involve curvature during propagation (Oda and Kazama, 1998). These characteristics were also observed in the simulations. Notably, in cases with two or more shear bands, no X-shaped shear band was observed, except for the fully symmetric cases discussed in Section 3.3. This observation aligns with experimental findings, whereas X-shaped shear bands are frequently reported in DEM simulations. This discrepancy may be attributed to the relatively simple contact models used in DEM, while FEM allows for the incorporation of more advanced constitutive models, enabling the simulation of more complex material behavior. Although a single sample rarely exhibits internal symmetry in shear band patterns, an inter-sample symmetry was identified. For example, the position and orientation of shear bands in different samples appear to show a form of symmetry (see Fig. 4(e) and (f)). This may indicate a global bifurcation phenomenon, where the formation of multiple shear bands resembles diffuse bifurcations (Yamakawa et al., 2018).

Finally, it should be noted that shear bands are generally more easily identified in numerical simulations than in physical experiments. In laboratory tests, they typically become visible only after propagating fully through the specimen and causing detectable displacement on the membrane surface (Shapiro and Yamamuro, 2003; Borja et al., 2013).

3.2. Representative Macroscopic Curve

3.2.1. Definition of Macroscopic Variables

In practical plane strain and axisymmetric triaxial experiments, although clear shear bands may appear in the specimen, the recorded shear stress and shear strain are always zero. Moreover, only a single set of global measurements is available per specimen, such as axial stress, confining pressure, axial and radial strain, and void ratio. In contrast,

numerical simulations provide detailed data at each integration point, including shear components and other variables.

Therefore, it is necessary to define a method to derive a global representation or macroscopic measurement from all integration point data, namely, to establish a connection between the micro-scale response and the macro-scale behavior. There are multiple strategies to achieve this, but a key criterion must be satisfied: when the void ratio is uniformly distributed, the representative curve extracted from a multi-element simulation should match that of a single-element simulation.

In this study, the following approach is used to obtain global representation.

The axial strain ϵ_1 is directly determined by the prescribed axial displacement. At each incremental loading step, nodal displacements are recorded, and lateral strain can be computed from the displacements at the lateral boundaries of the model (Fig. 5(a)). The vertical stress (axial stress σ_1) is calculated at each loading step by using the reaction forces at the top and bottom boundaries (Fig. 5(b) and (c)), together with the real-time lengths of those boundaries.

As shown in Fig. 5(b) and (c), the end-boundary force distribution becomes nearly uniform only before the shear band fully forms. This observation is consistent with experimental findings on lateral pressure behavior (Chu and Wanatowski, 2009), suggesting that the uniformity of mechanical response can serve as an indicator of the progression of strain localization. More importantly, once the shear band develops, stress and strain values derived from local measurements can no longer represent the behavior of the entire element. By using the reaction force of boundary nodes and real-time length, the axial stress is computed as follows:

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{\sum F_{1,bot} + \left(\sum F_{1,top} + p_0 \right)}{2L} \quad (6)$$

where F_1 denotes the nodal reaction force along the axial direction, with ‘bot’ and ‘top’ indicating the locations of the boundary nodes, and L is the real-time cross-sectional length computed from the boundary lengths. This equation may be modified according to specific FEM implementation and sign convention. For the intermediate principal stress acting in the plane (i.e., σ_{22}), a representative value for the specimen can be obtained by averaging across all integration points.

Fig. 5. Global representation by (a) lateral displacement; (b) vertical reaction force without shear band; (c) vertical reaction force with shear band.

However, this component is typically not recorded in standard plane strain tests.

Using the above method, the global representations of stress and strain can be obtained. Next, the Roscoe variables are defined. Since the global response of the specimen involves only the three principal stresses (with no shear components), the shear stress is described using the formulation proposed by [Finno et al. \(1997\)](#):

$$p' = \frac{\text{tr}(\sigma)}{3} \tag{7}$$

$$q_g = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)^2]} \tag{8}$$

However, for analyses at the element or integration point level, the shear stress component σ_{12} is generally non-zero. Therefore, the generalized shear stress is used to compute q :

$$q_e = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}S_{ij}S_{ij}} \tag{9}$$

$$q_e = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}[(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)^2] + 3(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2 + \sigma_{23}^2)} \tag{10}$$

Here, the subscript g refers to global representation and e refers to element-level values, and $S_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \frac{\delta_{ij}\text{tr}(\sigma)}{3}$.

Strain quantities are computed in a consistent way for both the element level and the global level, following ([Borja and Andrade, 2006](#)):

$$\varepsilon_q = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}\varepsilon_{ij}^*\varepsilon_{ij}^*} \tag{11}$$

where $\varepsilon_{ij}^* = \varepsilon_{ij} - \frac{\delta_{ij}\text{tr}(\varepsilon)}{3}$ is the deviatoric strain tensor. Due to large shear deformations, volumetric strain cannot be simply computed by summing

(a) 2D variability ($D_0 = 0.2, p_0 = 0.1 \text{ MPa}$)

(b) Only vertical variability ($D_0 = 0.2, p_0 = 0.55 \text{ MPa}$)

Fig. 6. Evolution of macroscopic shear resistance and ε_{12} distribution (colored contour).

the principal components of the strain tensor (Finno et al., 1997). Instead, it is defined using the deformation gradient F as:

$$\varepsilon_{v,e} = 1 - \det(F) \quad (12)$$

The macroscopic volumetric strain is then obtained by averaging over all elements:

$$\varepsilon_{v,g} = \frac{1}{n_e} \sum \varepsilon_{v,e} \quad (13)$$

The intermediate principal stress ratio is defined as

$$b = \frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{\sigma_1 - \sigma_3} \quad (14)$$

3.2.2. Stress Behavior

Using the definitions described above, a global representative curve can be obtained. This section focuses on the evolution of shear stress. Fig. 6 shows the evolution of shear stress, where the colored contours show the distribution of shear strain ε_{12} at given frame. Specifically, Fig. 6(a) shows the results of the simulation with one shear band, and Fig. 6(b) shows the results with two shear bands.

(1) Peak deviatoric stress.

According to Chu and Wanatowski (2009a), the peak shear stress is influenced by factors such as specimen size and experimental conditions (e.g., confining pressure). In the simulations presented in this study, for samples with 2D heterogeneity, the peak of q_g generally occurs before 3 % axial strain, mostly between 2 % and 3 %, which is consistent with experimental observations (Alshibli et al., 2003; Wanatowski and Chu, 2006; Wanatowski et al., 2008; Chu and Wanatowski, 2009). However, for samples exhibiting heterogeneity only in the vertical direction, the occurrence of peak shear stress is delayed. Due to the symmetry in geometry and boundary conditions, strain localization also displays a symmetric pattern, as illustrated in Fig. 6(b).

(2) Evolution of shear stress.

The evolution of shear stress is closely tied to the development of internal strain within the specimen. DIC (Digital Image Correlation) experiments have shown that even prior to peak shear stress, strain is already non-uniformly distributed (Nguyen et al., 2022). This is expected, as strain localization develops progressively, the specimen transitions from a uniform strain field to one characterized by distinct localized deformation, as shown in Fig. 6. Teunissen (2008) (Teunissen, 2008) suggested that the peak strength marks the onset of bifurcation. Similarly, Wanatowski and Chu (2012) proposed that the onset of shear bands could be identified as the point where the four recorded σ_2 values start to diverge.

Further, advanced experimental analyses have revealed that pronounced strain localization can occur before the peak shear stress is reached (Desrues et al., 2018). High-resolution LS-DEM simulations have also demonstrated that shear bands may begin to form well before the maximum stress is achieved (Kawamoto et al., 2018). The simulations in this study support these findings. Prior to reaching the peak q_g , multiple regions within the specimen exhibit localized stress and strain, but no distinct divergence or dominant shear band is observed (see Fig. 6). However, from the peak stress onward, shear strain begins to diverge significantly. One or two dominant shear bands emerge, and previously existing localized zones in these directions start to connect and expand toward the boundaries. Eventually, they form a continuous shear band, which signals the transition to residual strength. This observation is consistent with DIC experimental results, which show that before peak shear stress, shear bands are wide and diffuse, but after the peak, they become narrower and more concentrated (Takano et al., 2015).

(3) Fluctuation after peak stress.

The simulation further reveals that even above or below the main shear band, localized strain may continue to develop, though at a much smaller magnitude. Even within the shear band, further local compac-

tion may still appear, albeit with limited intensity (Takano et al., 2015). These factors contribute to fluctuations in q_g following the peak. The stiffness of the shear band may differ from that of the surrounding material and is generally lower than the unloading stiffness outside the band. Lin et al. (2015) attributed this re-hardening behavior to the shear band growing far enough to reach the vertical boundaries of the mesh, thereby restricting further development of shear band.

However, unlike DEM simulations (Thornton and Zhang, 2006; Mahmood and Iwashita, 2011; Wu et al., 2020; Zhou and Yin, 2023), the FEM simulations do not exhibit frequent stress reversals or fluctuations in shear stress during loading. This difference arises because, in DEM, particle rearrangement and the evolution of contact networks introduce numerous small-scale strain localization zones around the primary shear band, leading to more irregular shear responses.

(4) Divergence after peak stress.

Fig. 7 presents the global responses of samples with different realizations of the random field, namely, inhomogeneous cases 1 to 3, all of which share the same macroscopic initial density, covariance function, and correlation distance. In addition, a homogeneous case with the same initial density is also tested. While the overall behavior appears similar, variations between realizations lead to subtle differences in global response. Notably, all samples, regardless of inhomogeneity, exhibit nearly identical behavior before reaching the peak shear stress. In fact, the responses closely match that of the uniform sample simulation up to the peak.

However, after peak shear stress, the responses diverge significantly. Variations between different realizations become more pronounced, and the difference from the uniform sample also increases. This observation aligns with the conclusion of Chu and Leong (2001): strain softening before failure reflects an intrinsic material behavior, whereas post-failure softening arises from non-uniform deformation processes. The variation in strain localization behavior among different random field realizations is particularly evident during the early stages of shear band formation. These differences account for the divergence observed in post-peak responses.

3.3. Additional Void Ratio Distributions

Previous studies have explored strain localization using non-structured random fields (Borja and Andrade, 2006; Borja et al., 2013). However, a key limitation of those approaches is the absence of macroscopic void ratio constraints and the lack of consideration for spatial correlation. That said, the void ratio distribution model used in this study is also not without limitations; it only accounts for the macroscopic distribution and lacks directionally dependent variations or considerations of particle gradation. In physical experiments, sample preparation methods and the inclusion of fine particles can significantly affect the initial void distribution.

To investigate alternative initial void ratio models, additional simulations were carried out using specifically designed spatial distributions. Representative results are shown in Fig. 8. These include cases where the horizontal correlation distance is much greater than the vertical one (25,000 vs. 1, see Fig. 8 (a) and (b)), cases with heterogeneity only in the vertical direction (Fig. 8(c) and (d)), and cases with heterogeneity only in the horizontal direction, as shown in Fig. 8 (e) and (f).

Notably, the simulations show that the void ratio within the shear band can exceed the experimentally measured maximum value (1.054). This observation aligns with experimental findings, where the local void ratio in shear bands has been found to exceed the standard maximum void ratio determined by conventional methods (Oda and Kazama, 1998).

More importantly, the simulations suggest that variability of void ratio along the direction parallel to the principal loading direction is necessary for the formation of a shear band. These findings are consistent with results from phase-field modeling, which also revealed strain

Fig. 7. Global response of samples with and without inhomogeneity.

Fig. 8. Distribution of void ratio for samples with special initial conditions: (a, c, e) initial state; (b, d, f) final state.

localization in horizontally or quasi-horizontally layered structures (Ip and Borja, 2023). In idealized horizontal layering, the localized deformation zone tends to be symmetric. Real samples frequently exhibit near-horizontal layering (Semnani, 2018); However, as shown in Fig. 8, any departure from ideal horizontal layering can lead to the development of a fully connected shear band.

3.4. Hessian-Based Visualization of Void Ratio Field

In DEM simulations, rose diagrams are commonly used to visually compare fabric evolution before and after loading. A similar type of visual analysis can also be conducted in FEM. In this context, the void ratio is treated as a two-dimensional spatially varying field variable. To

quantify its spatial variation and identify patterns of anisotropy or localization, second-order spatial derivatives of the void ratio field can be computed to form the Hessian matrix at each point. The Hessian, defined as

$$H(x,y) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 e(x,y)}{\partial x^2} & \frac{\partial^2 e(x,y)}{\partial x \partial y} \\ \frac{\partial^2 e(x,y)}{\partial x \partial y} & \frac{\partial^2 e(x,y)}{\partial y^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (15)$$

captures the local curvature properties of the state variable field $e(x,y)$. By performing an eigen analysis of $H(x,y)$, its eigenvalues and corresponding eigenvectors can be easily obtained. The principal eigenvector

v , associated with the larger eigenvalue, indicates the direction of maximum curvature variation at given point. The orientation of this principal eigenvector, considering the proper quadrant, is given by

$$\theta(x, y) = \text{atan2}(v_y, v_x) \tag{16}$$

where atan2 is the two-argument arctangent function; v_x and v_y are the x and y components of the principal eigenvector v , respectively. This angle provides a quantitative measure of the local directional variability of the field. And the distribution of angles can be visually analyzed to check the variability and homogeneity of corresponding field variables. Once the orientation $\theta(x, y)$ of the principal direction is obtained at each spatial point, the dominating direction can be quantified by calculating the circular mean of $\theta(x, y)$. This is given by:

$$\bar{\theta} = \text{atan2}\left(\sum_i \sin\theta(x_i, y_i), \sum_i \cos\theta(x_i, y_i)\right) \tag{17}$$

To illustrate this concept, Fig. 9 (a) and (b) present an example showing the variation of the curvature direction (expressed by arrows) of the void ratio field (indicated by colored contours) before and after loading, respectively. Fig. 9(c) shows rose plots of the curvature directions.

The results show that the globally dominating direction changes very little before and after shear band formation, typically within 4 degrees. This suggests that significant deformation is limited to local regions. The rose diagram further reveals that the principal eigenvectors tend to align in a specific direction, and this clustered orientation corresponds to the normal direction of the shear band.

4. Regional Behavior

A shear band is a smooth and continuously varying zone of intense deformation, characterized by very large shear strains (Rudnicki and Rice, 1975). For samples exhibiting shear bands, Le et al. (2022) divided the model domain into a localization band and the surrounding bulk material. The mechanical behavior within and outside the band differs significantly (Zhou and Yin, 2023), and this section investigates such

differences in detail.

4.1. Initialization and Evolution of the Shear Band

Suzuki and Yamada (2006) suggested that the dilatancy index–strain curve may reveal physical trends more clearly than the traditional stress–strain curve. In this section, we compare the evolution of global dilatancy and shear stress with respect to axial strain, as shown in Fig. 10. In the figure, a negative value of $d\varepsilon_v/d\varepsilon_1$ indicates dilatative, and this quantity is the negative of the dilatancy index defined in Suzuki and Yamada (2006).

A fundamental concept in soil mechanics is the critical state, which refers to a condition where the material reaches constant volume after sufficient shearing. However, the development of shear bands complicates the observation of the critical state (Mooney et al., 1998). The results in Fig. 10 also highlight the influence of the initial state. Fig. 10 (a) and (b) show initially loose samples, which exhibit almost no further volumetric change in the post-peak stage. In contrast, Fig. 10(c) and (d) correspond to initially dense samples, which continue to exhibit slow volumetric expansion even after the peak. This indicates that, even though dilatancy within a persistent shear band may approach zero, localized volumetric behavior still exists, as also pointed out by Finno et al. (1997) (Finno et al., 1997).

By combining the stress evolution discussed in Section 3.2.2 with the dilatancy behavior shown here, the loading process can be generally divided into three stages:

- (1) Stage 1: From the beginning of loading up to the peak shear stress. During this phase, local strains develop in different regions. As the peak is approached, certain localized zones begin to preferentially align along dominant directions. These zones show signs of extension but have not yet reached the boundaries, and a dominant shear band has not fully formed.
- (2) Stage 2: After the peak stress, as localized shear bands have already developed significantly, a dominant shear band begins to grow toward the boundaries along a preferred direction and rapidly connects across the domain. During this process, the

Fig. 9. Orientation distribution of principal Hessian eigenvectors: (a) Before loading; (b) After loading; (c) Rose plots.

(a) Double shear bands ($D_0 = 0.2, p_0 = 0.1MPa$) (b) Single shear band ($D_0 = 0.2, p_0 = 0.1MPa$)

(c) Double shear bands ($D_0 = 0.9, p_0 = 0.55MPa$) (d) Single shear band ($D_0 = 0.9, p_0 = 0.55MPa$)

Fig. 10. Evolution of global dilatancy and global shear stress.

initially dominant band may be overtaken by another band forming in a conjugate direction, a phenomenon also discussed in Finno et al. (1997) as the emergence of the final shear band.

- (3) Stage 3: Localized strain continues to develop in regions outside the shear band. However, due to the presence of a fully developed shear band, the extent of this strain is highly limited, resulting in minor fluctuations in deviatoric stress (i.e., small oscillations in q_s). Ultimately, the system reaches residual strength, which, according to Teunissen (2008), is governed by the strength within the shear band itself, as is also the case for peak strength.

It is important to note that this stage-based classification is based on macroscopic responses. At the integration-point level, the stress-strain histories can be highly irregular. For example, Fig. 11 illustrates the results from a simulation with $D_0 = 0.9$ and $p_0 = 0.55MPa$, where the stress-strain behaviour of individual integration points shows clear deviations from the global response and the simulation results of homogenous sample.

As shown in Figs. 10 and 11, compared to homogeneous samples, a distinctive feature of simulations with inhomogeneous samples is the earlier onset of dilatancy. Notably, the maximum dilatant strength is reached almost simultaneously with the reversal in shear stress growth. This observation is consistent with experimental findings, where the peak of dilatant strength coincides with the initiation of shear band formation. At this point, contiguous regions of localized dilation begin to coalesce, marking the formation of the shear band.

Fig. 11. Global response and local responses.

4.2. Geometric Characteristics of Shear Bands

4.2.1. Orientation

The inclination angle of shear bands has been extensively investigated in plane strain and triaxial tests (Mühlhaus and Vardoulakis, 1987). This angle, measured with respect to the plane orthogonal to the loading direction, is influenced by the stress-strain state (Kawamoto et al., 2018).

As deformation progresses, the orientation of the shear band increases on average by 3° (Finno et al., 1997). In biaxial numerical simulations, the shear band inclination is reported to be in the range of

54.5°–57° (Tejchman and Bauer, 1996). Confining pressure has also been shown to influence the orientation of shear bands in plane strain conditions (Han and Drescher, 1993). In triaxial tests, the inclination angle relative to the horizontal ranges between 47° and 54° (Andò et al., 2012). In plane strain tests, the inclination angle θ for medium-loose sand ranges between 49.0° and 57.5°, and between 49.6° and 58.6° for medium-dense sand. The average values are 55.6° and 56.2 % respectively.

Generally, elasto-plastic models allow the failure surface orientation to fall between the Coulomb and Roscoe directions. The Coulomb direction (θ_C) and the Roscoe direction (θ_R) are defined as follows (Wu et al., 2020):

$$\theta_C = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{q_{\max}}{P' q_{\max}} \right) \quad (18)$$

and

$$\theta_R = \frac{\pi}{4} + \frac{\Psi_{\max}}{2} \quad (19)$$

respectively. The dilatancy angle Ψ , applicable to triaxial, simple shear, and drained plane strain conditions, can be calculated as (Maranha and Maranhã Das Neves, 2009):

$$\sin \psi = - \frac{de_1^p + de_2^p}{de_1^p - de_2^p} \quad (20)$$

where compressive strains are taken as positive. According to Teunissen (2008) (Teunissen, 2008), strain localization can occur along directions between the Roscoe and Coulomb orientations. Compared to bands closer to the Coulomb angle, those near the Roscoe angle tend to exhibit more gradual strength degradation. Roscoe’s solution has been shown to better predict shear band inclination (Wanatowski et al., 2008). Consistently, the numerical results in this study align more closely with the Roscoe angle regardless of the specific realization of the random field. Both the location and orientation of the shear bands are comparable with experimental observations in Ottawa sand and Hostun sand (Andò et al., 2013; Alikarami et al., 2015; Takano et al., 2015).

4.2.2. Thickness

In both experiments and discrete element simulations (DEM), shear band thickness can be visually identified. Particle size, particularly the median diameter d_{50} , plays a major role in determining the band width (Soltani and Maekawa, 2015).

Using X-ray computed tomography, Nohara and Mukunoki (2021) found that the shear band thickness is approximately 7.1 times d_{50} , which is consistent with earlier findings (Oda and Kazama, 1998). Other studies have reported values ranging from 12.6 to 15.5 times d_{50} , based on a factor of 3.9/0.31 to 4.8/0.31 (Alikarami et al., 2015; Le et al., 2022). Additional results include approximately 10 times d_{50} (Andò et al., 2012; Kawamoto et al., 2018) and 6–12 times d_{50} (Andò et al., 2012).

In plane strain conditions, where normal displacement is constrained, lateral expansion is enhanced, leading to a wider shear band. Theoretically, the thickness can reach 16 times d_{50} (Mühlhaus and Vardoulakis, 1987) or even 20 times d_{50} (Vardoulakis and Aifantis, 1991). Simulated results from biaxial tests suggest band widths of 10–13 times d_{50} (Tejchman and Bauer, 1996), while DEM studies report 15–18 times the average particle radius (Thornton and Zhang, 2006). Further DEM simulation suggested that the width of shear band varies from 10 d_{50} to 40 d_{50} , (mostly fluctuates around 26 d_{50}) (Liu et al., 2018) and its evolution can be captured by spatial dynamic analysis (Ma et al., 2019). Experimental observations have recorded a range of 10.63 to 20 times d_{50} , depending on confining pressure and initial density (Alshibli and Sture, 1999).

In finite element (FEM) simulations, the thickness of the shear band

can be identified by observing zones where the shear strain gradient changes abruptly, which marks the boundary between the bulk material and the shear band. As shown in Fig. 12(a), the shear band spans approximately $\sqrt{2}$ to 3 elements in thickness, corresponding to a physical width of 1.8 to 3.75 mm, based on an element size of 1.25 mm². The constitutive parameters used in this study correspond to Karlsruhe fine sand, with a median particle diameter $d_{50} = 0.14$ mm, indicating that the shear band thickness is approximately 12.6 to 26.8 times d_{50} .

According to Tejchman and Bauer (1996), when the element size is smaller than five times d_{50} , the calculated thickness of the shear band becomes nearly independent of the mesh size. Therefore, simulations were also conducted using a finer mesh of 0.5 mm × 0.5 mm. As shown in Fig. 12(b), the shear band thickness varies between approximately $\sqrt{2}$ mm and $2\sqrt{2}$ mm. This corresponds to 10 to 20 times d_{50} , which is in good agreement with experimental observations.

4.3. Deformation and Void ratio

To further investigate the difference in mechanical response between regions inside and outside the shear band, a cross-sectional line was drawn perpendicular to the band orientation after the shear band had fully developed. Along this line, shear strain and displacement magnitudes were extracted for each element. The results are shown in Fig. 13. Consistent with experimental and discrete element method (DEM) studies, the shear band is a zone of concentrated incremental deviatoric strain and rotation (Kawamoto et al., 2018). It also serves as a distinct boundary in the displacement field, where deformation is localized on one side of the band, while the opposite side experiences negligible displacement.

To further explore this behavior, the evolution of void ratio in the shear band and surrounding areas was monitored at multiple time steps during loading. The void ratio values of elements along the same cross-sectional line were recorded over successive frames, and the results are presented in Fig. 14. Similar to experimental observations (Kido and Higo, 2017), changes in void ratio were largely confined to the shear

Fig. 12. Shear strain (ϵ_{12}) under different element sizes: (a) 1.25 mm²; (b) 0.5 mm².

Fig. 13. Displacement and deformation fields within and outside the shear band.

band.

Within the band, void ratio tends to become more spatially uniform over time. In other words, initially loose zones exhibit a decrease in void ratio, while initially dense regions exhibit an increase (Lin et al., 2015). This redistribution leads to a reduced contrast between the local maximum and minimum void ratio values within the shear band. In contrast, the void ratio variation outside the band remains largely unchanged throughout loading.

As highlighted by Desrues et al. (1996), such localization of void ratio evolution suggests that global measurements may be insufficient to characterize the volumetric behavior of dense granular specimens undergoing large strains in triaxial conditions. This reflects a clear distinction between macroscopic and local void ratio responses.

5. Mechanism Analysis

5.1. Shear Strain Localization

To investigate the influence of state variable inhomogeneity on strain localization, as well as the role of boundary conditions, the model can be simplified to an isotropic linear elastic framework, which depends only on two parameters: the elastic modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν .

In the case where variability exists only in the direction perpendicular to loading, as illustrated in Fig. 15(a), except for a fixed point at the center of the bottom boundary, adjacent soil columns are free to expand laterally. In this configuration, the horizontal and vertical deformations satisfy:

$$\begin{cases} E_g \epsilon_{g,y} = E_1 \epsilon_{g,y} + E_2 \epsilon_{g,y} \\ \epsilon_{1,x} = \nu_1 \epsilon_{g,y} \neq \nu_2 \epsilon_{g,y} = \epsilon_{2,x} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

and

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\epsilon_{1,y}}{\epsilon_{2,y}} = 1 \\ \frac{\epsilon_{1,x}}{\epsilon_{2,x}} = \frac{\nu_1}{\nu_2} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

where the subscripts '1' and '2' correspond to component numbers; the subscripts x and y denote the directions, namely the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. This implies uniform vertical deformation. Although horizontal deformation varies across columns, the absence of boundary friction prevents the development of shear stresses or strains. As a result, no shear band forms under this condition.

When heterogeneity exists only along the loading direction, as in Fig. 15(b), the system satisfies:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\epsilon_{1,y}}{\epsilon_{2,y}} = \frac{E_2}{E_1} \\ \frac{\epsilon_{1,x}}{\epsilon_{2,x}} = \epsilon_{1,y} \epsilon_{2,y} \frac{\nu_1}{\nu_2} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

In this case, while vertical deformation within each horizontal layer is uniform, lateral expansion varies between layers. This mismatch generates relative rotations between adjacent layers, leading to shear strains and shear stresses. Although, in theory, a special combination of mate-

(a) Slicing frames

(b) Shear strain

(c) Void ratio

Fig. 14. Evolutionary distribution of void ratio and shear strain across the shear band.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 15. Schematic elastic fields with: (a) horizontal variability only; (b) vertical variability only; and (c) both vertical and horizontal variability.

rial parameters could eliminate shear stress (i.e., when $\frac{\epsilon_{1y}\epsilon_{2y}\nu_1}{\nu_2} = 1$), such a condition is highly restrictive and not commonly met in practice.

When heterogeneity exists in both the horizontal and vertical directions, as shown in Fig. 15(c), deformation becomes non-uniform in both dimensions. This leads to complex patterns of relative distortion between adjacent nodes, resulting in more pronounced shear strain and

stress development.

In addition to structural inhomogeneity, boundary conditions play an important role in the development of strain localization. Fig. 8(f) and Fig. 15(a) show that when friction between the loading plate and the sample is not considered, and heterogeneity exists only in the horizontal direction, strain localization does not occur after loading. However,

when a non-zero friction coefficient μ is assumed between the rigid loading plate and the sample, Fig. 16 shows that strain localization does appear within the sample. The pattern of localization also changes with different values of μ . Conversely, if the free ends are properly installed to minimize end constraints, strain softening during drained tests can be prevented or significantly delayed (Chu and Lo, 1993).

5.2. Elastic Constitutive Model

According to Chu and Wanatowski (2009a), strain-softening behavior at the macroscopic scale may arise even when the material itself does not exhibit softening. This suggests that constitutive models incapable of capturing post-peak behavior can still be used to simulate apparent softening, provided the phenomenon is structurally induced. To further investigate whether the observed softening may be primarily structural rather than material in nature, this section adopts a simplified isotropic elastic model instead of advanced constitutive formulations. To account for the influence of void ratio, a void ratio-dependent elasticity is used. In this model, the elastic modulus E decreases linearly with increasing void ratio, following the relationship:

$$E = E_0 \left(\frac{e_M e_m}{e_M - e_m} \right) \quad (24)$$

where E_0 is the reference modulus, and e_m and e_M are the minimum and maximum void ratio values, respectively. The results under loading conditions with $D_0 = 0.9$ and $p_0 = 2$ MPa are shown in Fig. 17.

Although the initial state lacks symmetry, the distributions of shear strain and void ratio after loading exhibit an approximate point-symmetric pattern, as shown in Fig. 17. Since the material behaves elastically, no plastic deformation occurs, and the material stiffness remains high. This behavior is analogous to that of dense granular assemblies subjected to high confining pressures, where deformation tends to be dominated by structural constraints rather than material yielding, similar to the high-pressure conditions presented in Fig. 11 of (Alikarami et al., 2015). It is important to note that the formation of shear bands requires energy dissipation mechanisms, which are absent in purely elastic materials. As a result, while the simulation does not produce shear bands, it does exhibit clear stress and strain localization.

5.3. Onset and Propagation of Shear Bands

Dilatancy has been recognized as a reliable indicator of strain

localization (Suzuki and Yamada, 2006) and is also effective in characterizing shear band behavior (Finno et al., 1997). As dilatancy is highly sensitive to void ratio or relative density, this section explores the possibility of estimating shear band initiation and evolution based on the initial distribution of void ratio.

The orientation of the primary shear band in the simulations aligns well with previous studies in Section 4.2.1. Regardless of whether the direction is defined by the Mohr-Coulomb or Roscoe criteria, the angle between the shear band and the principal deformation direction remains relatively consistent. Therefore, to understand the development of shear bands, it is sufficient to identify the favorable zones for their formation and the paths through which these zones become connected.

The initiation and evolution of shear bands are closely associated with regions exhibiting high void ratio gradients. These regions may occur either at the boundaries or within the interior of the specimen. As a result, the initial concentration of shear strain may arise in either location. Fundamentally, such regions correspond to zones of high dilatancy contrast, as indicated by dense void ratio contours.

While considering the role of void ratio, two earlier observations are worth highlighting:

- (1) When a state-dependent plastic constitutive model is used and void ratio variability exists only in the direction perpendicular to loading, non-uniform deformation can still occur. However, this configuration does not lead to the development of shear stress or shear strain.
- (2) When void ratio varies along the loading direction and a void ratio-dependent elastic constitutive model is adopted, both non-uniform deformation and rotation are observed. In this case, shear stress and shear strain do develop, but the zones of concentration remain near the boundaries and do not propagate into the interior.

Based on these findings, this section aims to propose a conceptual explanation for the mechanism governing shear band formation.

Due to the complex interaction between the rubber membrane and the granular at the boundaries, regions with densely packed isolines of void ratio near the specimen edge may act as seeds for shear band formation. If large deformation is allowed in these zones, shear bands are most likely to emerge. However, these densely packed isolines, which represent steep gradients in void ratio, may correspond to either local peaks (relatively loose zones with higher void ratios) or troughs

Fig. 16. Shear strain field when axial strain is about 5.5 %: (a) $\mu = 0.1$; (b) $\mu = 0.2$

Fig. 17. Field distribution obtained from void ratio-dependent linear elasticity.

(relatively dense zones with lower void ratios). While shear band onset tends to occur in regions of steep void ratio gradients, the presence of multiple such regions does not guarantee full band development.

Due to the complex interaction between the rubber membrane and the granular material at the specimen boundaries, regions with densely packed isolines of void ratio near the edges may act as initial sites for shear band formation. If these zones are allowed to undergo large deformation, shear bands are most likely to emerge. These densely spaced isolines indicate steep gradients in void ratio, which may correspond to local peaks, representing relatively loose regions with higher void ratios, or to troughs, representing relatively dense regions with lower void ratios. Although the onset of shear bands often occurs in

regions with sharp void ratio variation, the presence of multiple such regions does not necessarily result in the development of a continuous shear band. If several densely contoured zones align along a favorable orientation, which is discussed in Section 4.2.1, and if the path connecting them passes through the transitional zones between relatively loose (peak) and dense (trough) areas, this alignment may evolve into a continuous shear band. This process is illustrated in Fig. 18 and Fig. 19, where regions with closely spaced contour lines indicate steep slopes or abrupt changes in void ratio.

From an energy perspective, greater external loading corresponds to greater energy dissipation for a given amount of plastic deformation. Under the same pressure level, denser regions exhibit higher stiffness

Fig. 18. Isoline plot of void ratio ($D_0 = 0.5, p_0 = 0.1MPa$) with void ratio-dependent elastic constitutive model: (a) initial state; (b). $\epsilon_{1g} = 0.25$

Fig. 19. Isoline plot of void ratio ($D_0 = 0.9$, $p_0 = 2MPa$) with plastic constitutive model: (a) initial state; (b) $\varepsilon_{1,g} = 0.025$; (c) $\varepsilon_{1,g} = 0.035$; (d) $\varepsilon_{1,g} = 0.0375$; (e). $\varepsilon_{1,g} = 0.05$

and greater dilatancy (Borja et al., 2013), both of which are closely linked to strain localization (Suzuki and Yamada, 2006; Soltanbeigi et al., 2021). Therefore, dense zones are capable of generating a higher energy dissipation density, making them more susceptible to strain localization. Once a continuous localization zone forms, it can accelerate global deformation and increase the overall dissipation rate. In this sense, the presence of void ratio (or other state variables) inhomogeneity provides the structural basis for the formation of energy dissipation pathways, facilitating the emergence and propagation of shear bands.

It is important to note that this is only one of several possible mechanisms for shear band formation. Micro defects such as fine containing can affect the development and final number of shear bands, reflecting the influence of local kinematics, especially those related to rotation, on global behavior (Gardiner and Tordesillas, 2004; Tordesillas et al., 2008). The evolution of shear bands is also significantly influenced by boundary conditions. According to Nicot et al. (2023), the system's maximum elastic energy storage capacity plays a crucial role in the transition from a homogeneous to a heterogeneous state. Under laterally confined compression, where the lateral stiffness is effectively infinite, the system can accumulate almost unlimited elastic strain energy in that direction. In such cases, the shear band formation mechanism described above may not be activated.

5.4. Limited Flow and Model Calibration

The phenomenon of limited flow, observed in some undrained tests, can be explained through the lens of inhomogeneous void ratio. In this section, an extremely simplified model is employed to illustrate this concept.

According to Wichtmann et al. (2020), specimens prepared using the moist tamping method exhibit contact normal vectors that are predominantly oriented in the vertical direction. This vertically biased microstructure implies that particle arrangements in the horizontal direction are more uniform and ordered, resulting in stronger horizontal structural consistency. In contrast, specimens prepared by air pluviation show a more dispersed distribution of contact normal (Kodicherla et al., 2018), lacking a clear preferential orientation. This leads to lower structural uniformity in the horizontal direction, more random inter-particle contacts, and increased anisotropy.

This enhanced horizontal uniformity in moist-tamped samples contributes to their higher strength and stiffness, as compared to air-pluviated samples with more randomly oriented and less coherent horizontal structures. These observations are consistent with both experimental findings and discrete element method (DEM) simulations.

To illustrate the mechanical consequence, a highly simplified model is introduced. In this model, suppose we have only two elements with different initial void ratio but they share the same constitutive model, as shown in Fig. 20. And a simple hypoplastic model (von Wolffersdorff, 1996) is used with its parameters listed in Table 1.

The macroscopic response of the inhomogeneous sample can be simulated under undrained loading. Further, if the specimen is homogeneous ($D_0 = 0.3$, and D_0 is the same for both elements 1 and 2), a uniform response is obtained. However, as shown in Fig. 20 (b) and (c), the responses of two elements within the specimen diverge significantly from the uniform assumption. One point exhibits a flow-type response, while the other shows a non-flow response. At the macroscopic level, however, the overall behavior corresponds to limited flow.

In experimental practice, what is recorded is the global (macroscopic) response of the specimen, such as the overall stress–strain or stress–pore pressure curves. These responses are typically used for the development and calibration of constitutive models. However, as illustrated in Fig. 20, model calibration based solely on these macroscopic curves can lead to significant discrepancies between the identified parameters and the actual material behavior. The true constitutive response, which corresponds to the behavior at integration points within a numerical model or local zones in real specimens, cannot be directly captured through simply global measurements. Therefore, as noted by Desrues and Chambon (2002), only specialized tests such as the hollow cylinder torsional shear test, or more advanced laboratory setups, can reliably capture and calibrate the shear modulus and other local mechanical properties.

Furthermore, the loading mode also plays a significant role in shaping the macroscopic response. As shown in experimental studies (Chu and Wanatowski, 2009), drained plane strain tests allow for more effective investigation of post-peak behavior under displacement control (DC), particularly the development of steady-state shear (Chu and Leong, 2001). In DC mode, strain softening behavior is typically observed, characterized by a decrease in stress with increasing strain, that is, $d\sigma < 0$ (Valanis, 1985). This results in a residual shear stress level after the peak. In contrast, load control (LC) tests are more prone to instability, typically manifested as a continuous drop in shear stress and rapid accumulation of axial strain. Although the observed phenomena differ, the conditions that lead to both strain softening and instability are fundamentally the same. Thus, for a given stress–strain history, the macroscopic response of the specimen is strongly influenced by the loading mode. This interplay between material behavior, structural response, and boundary effects cannot be adequately captured by constitutive modeling alone.

φ_c	h_s/MPa	n	e_{d0}	e_{c0}	e_{i0}	α	β
0.577	4e3	0.27	0.677	1.054	1.212	0.14	2.5

Fig. 20. Macroscopic limited flow by inhomogeneous state field: (a) diagram of undrained simulation; (b) and (c): micro- and macro- response.

Table 1
Material parameters of hypoplasticity for illustration.

φ_c	h_s/MPa	n	e_{d0}	e_{c0}	e_{i0}	α	β
0.577	4e3	0.27	0.677	1.054	1.212	0.14	2.5

6. Conclusion

Accurately distinguishing between material behavior and other forms of behavior, such as structural responses, from laboratory test records is both important and challenging. The presence of structured inhomogeneity in the state variables of a specimen further complicates this task and often makes it intractable to distinguish the true material response. Laboratory specimens are typically small in size, and while the material used may be homogeneous in composition (implying a common constitutive model and set of parameters), the distribution of state variables can still be highly non-uniform. Among these, void ratio is the most fundamental. To better evaluate the effect of initial void ratio inhomogeneity on the observed macroscopic response, this study systematically reviews related research and further performs numerical simulations under idealized boundary conditions using multiple sets of structured inhomogeneous samples. Based on the literature review and extended simulation results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

(1) Shear bands observed in experiments may arise from structural behavior induced by initial inhomogeneity rather than purely from material behavior. Even when using a relatively simple

constitutive model, a non-uniform distribution of void ratio alone can lead to complex macroscopic responses. These include the overall shear stress response, the initiation and evolution of shear bands, their geometric characteristics, mechanical behavior within and outside the bands, and limited flow phenomena. However, inhomogeneity in void ratio alone cannot fully explain all observed behaviors. For example, similar initial void ratio and anisotropic conditions may still result in different stress-strain responses (Pan et al., 2024).

- (2) Under ideal boundary conditions, the onset of shear bands require heterogeneity along the loading direction. In contrast, heterogeneity perpendicular to the loading direction alone is insufficient to trigger localization. Therefore, when the degree of heterogeneity parallel to the loading direction is much smaller than that in the perpendicular direction, the macroscopic effects of strain localization can be minimized. This insight has practical implications for specimen preparation, where uniformity along the loading direction should be prioritized to reduce structural effects.
- (3) Even using an extremely simplified structural analysis, the role of inhomogeneous void ratio can be clearly demonstrated. The underlying mechanism lies in the variation in stiffness among different regions in the specimen. When coupled with specific boundary conditions, such stiffness heterogeneity can produce a wide range of complex macroscopic behaviors. Therefore, initial inhomogeneity must be considered alongside other influential factors during both experimental interpretation and constitutive model development. If the effects of boundary constraints and

inhomogeneity are not properly accounted for, the resulting model and parameters can not represent true material behavior.

- (4) Strain localization is fundamentally the manifestation of a non-uniform strain gradient. An initially inhomogeneous state naturally leads to spatial variations in strain gradients. Local peaks and depressions in state variables can contribute to the onset of shear bands, while the development of these bands further amplifies the spatial variation of state parameters, forming distinct ridges or valleys. Since void ratio is only one among many state variables influencing stiffness, it is reasonable to infer that inhomogeneity in other relevant state variables may also induce similar localization patterns, provided that the constitutive model adequately captures the state-dependent nature of the material response and appropriate boundary conditions are applied.
- (5) Conventional laboratory tests are theoretically designed with simple stress and strain paths, which help simplify the development and calibration of constitutive models. However, in practice, the internal structure of the specimen and the boundary conditions are far from ideal. This makes it difficult to inversely identify the true material behavior from test data. Nevertheless, test records still generally reflect the material response, especially before significant strain localization occurs. In future studies, if conditions allow, it may be more valuable to focus on better control of the specimen, test equipment, and procedures rather than aiming for simple stress paths. Such test results can provide more reliable guidance for the development of constitutive models.

Several factors can significantly influence the macroscopic response. These include material behavior, the initial state of the specimen, interactions between the specimen and the experimental apparatus (such as loading plates or rubber membranes), and the applied loading mode. To fully decouple these influences and isolate the true material behavior from laboratory test data, further research is required. The key directions for such work include the following:

- (1) Improvement of simulation methods. Finite element methods (FEM) have inherent limitations, particularly their inability to capture the influence of grain shape (Alikarami et al., 2015, Liu et al., 2025). By faithfully replicating both the particle morphology and the boundary conditions of granular assemblies in simulations, the formation and evolution of shear bands can also be clearly observed (Kawamoto et al., 2018). Nonetheless, FEM has important advantages, especially its ability to incorporate more advanced constitutive models compared to particle-based methods. This strength is also demonstrated in the present study.
- (2) Coupled analysis of influencing factors. Inhomogeneity in void ratio alone cannot fully explain the observed macroscopic behaviors. In addition to the aspects discussed in this study, other factors such as particle morphology also influence the mechanical response (Zhao et al., 2021), although they are not captured in the current framework.
- (3) Theoretical modeling of inhomogeneous state variables. Further research is required to develop models that are both physically grounded and statistically representative. For instance, statistical models derived from large datasets of laboratory measurements could be employed to guide the generation of spatially correlated random fields. Alternatively, physics-based formulations describing the macroscopic distribution of state variables may be proposed to better capture the governing mechanisms of inhomogeneity.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zhihui Wang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Roberto Cudmani:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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